

The challenges of waterborne pathogens: A review

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Key Points:

- Waterborne diseases continue to pose significant challenges to global public health and represent a considerable environmental concern.
- Diarrhea, leptospirosis, giardiasis, typhoid fever, salmonellosis, shigellosis, rotavirus diarrhea, *E. coli* diarrhea, and Hepatitis A are waterborne diseases often brought on by pathogenic microorganisms.
- More efficient microbiological monitoring, pathogen detection, and health risk assessment must be included to achieve the objective of pathogen-free water.

Abstract

All living things depend on water and water resources to maintain a healthy habitat and obtain an adequate food supply. The need for water is increasing along with the global population. Nonetheless, water resources are depleting, becoming more contaminated, and being exploited unconsciously due to various factors, including human activity. Microbial pollution is considered a significant public health concern. Numerous microorganisms can contaminate water and cause diseases. Diarrhea, leptospirosis, giardiasis, typhoid fever, salmonellosis, shigellosis, rotavirus diarrhea, *E. coli* diarrhea, and Hepatitis A are waterborne diseases often brought on by pathogenic microorganisms. The World Health Organization recommends that rather than directly detecting the pathogens, the microbiological quality of the drinking water be assessed using faecal indicator bacteria, particularly *Escherichia coli*, which signal the presence of faecal contamination. Thus, a water quality monitoring plan is necessary to safeguard the water resources, as water quality is becoming a serious issue in many countries, especially due to the concern that freshwater may become scarce in the future. This review thus highlights the importance of water quality and the potential risk of waterborne pathogens.

Keywords: Water quality, Contamination, Faecal contamination, Pathogens.

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1. Introduction

Over two thirds of the earth is covered with water, yet much of it is salty and unfit for human consumption. Only 2.7% of the water on earth is available as freshwater; barely one percent of that freshwater found in lakes, rivers, and groundwater is usable. Since the majority of freshwater resources are found in glaciers (in the polar ice) and deep aquifers, buried parts of the hydrologic cycles, they are inaccessible. Only about 3% of the freshwater resources on earth are made up of drinking water (Binns et al., 2001; DWA, 2011).

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 2.6 billion people do not have access to clean water, and that illnesses associated to water kills 3.4 million people annually, the majority of whom are children (WHO, [Water Sanitation and Health, 2010](#)). It is estimated that about 4,000 people, including over 1,000 children under five, die each day as a result of contaminated water (United Nations Children's Fund report, (UNICEF), 2023) . In developing nations where sanitation, water purification, and hygiene practices are not taken seriously, the drinking water pollution caused by microorganisms is not unusual, and

the ensuing disease endemics or epidemics are common (Acharjee et al., 2011; Ahmed et al., 2013). Pathogenic microorganism-contaminated water poses a significantly higher risk to public health (Wen et al., 2020). Since the majority of the pathogens linked to disease transmission are found in the feces of warm-blooded animals and humans, faecal pollution is the primary source of waterborne diseases (Paruch et al., 2019). The microbial pollution is thought to have an impact on public health, since waterborne illnesses such as diarrhea, typhoid fever, and Bacillary dysentery are typically caused by infections by harmful bacteria (Onyango et al., 2018). The presence of both non-coliform species like heterotrophic bacteria and total coliform bacteria may cause special health risks for infants, young children and immune-compromised adults (Sharon et al., 2013). According to Million Death Study Collaborators (2010), diarrhea is the third leading cause of mortality for children under five years old. It accounts for 13% of all deaths in this age group, which means that 300,000 children in India die from diarrhea every year. Using available data, Bivins et al. (2017) studied the conservative risk proxies for bacterial, protozoan, and viral infections using reference pathogens *Campylobacter*, *Cryptosporidium*, and *Rotavirus*, respectively. Their research found that, the median daily risk of infection for *Campylobacter*, *Cryptosporidium*, and *Rotavirus* was 1 in 23,500, 1 in 5,050,000, and 1 in 118,000, respectively. According to Edberg et al. (2000), *E. coli* has been used as a biological indication of water treatment efficacy since the 1890s. Enteric pathogens such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Vibrio* spp., and others can cause gastroenteritis (cholera, diarrhea, dysentery, etc.) in consumers, if the water is not processed adequately (Acharjee et al., 2011; Acharjee et al., 2013; Cray et al., 1995; Mahbub et al., 2011; Munshi et al., 2012). The World Health Organization recommends that, rather than directly detecting pathogens, the microbiological quality of the drinking water be assessed using faecal indicator bacteria, particularly *E. coli*, which signal the presence of faecal contamination (WHO, 2008). Improving the water quality can reduce the global illness burden by about 4% (WHO, Water Sanitation and Health, 2010). Thus, this review reveals the risk caused by waterborne pathogens and the significance of water quality.

2. The importance of water

Water is a vital resource for life on earth, and both people and the ecosystem should have access to clean water

(Tazoe, 2023). Water is a living space and one of the fundamental elements that build the environment for life. Water has consistently been the primary determinant of residential regions and a key component in the building of civilizations throughout history (Çepel and Ergun, 2003). The importance of water bodies is given in Figure 1.

For all living things to survive, freshwater is necessary. People depend on it for industrial processes, food production, trash disposal, and cultural requirements, making it more significant to them (APHA, AWWA and WEF, 2012). Sahin (2016) reported that water consumption has increased seven folds in the last century. The worldwide supply of potable water is being progressively depleted over time due to factors like imbalanced urbanization, rapid population expansion, excessive industrialization, water pollution by dumping of waste. All the organisms are getting deprived of water, which is the source of life, due to a number of causes including pollution of already limited amounts of usable and potable water resources, unsuitability of water used in energy production for human consumption after recycling, uncontrolled pesticide use, improper agricultural practices, water waste, changes in climate due to global warming, drought, lack of knowledge about water etc. (Kılıc, 2020).

2.1. Water quality and Waterborne diseases

One of the most serious emerging ecological issues that nations worldwide are currently dealing with is water quality (Bilal et al., 2023). Both ecological sustainability and urban growth depend on the quantity and quality of water available. Significant water security challenges are increasingly affecting the world's population (Vörösmarty et al., 2010). A large number of developing nations lack wastewater treatment infrastructure, and many of their citizens rely on severely contaminated surface water sources, which can lead to outbreaks of waterborne illnesses (Islam and Afroz, 2019). A wide range of microorganisms can pollute surface water from several sources, including septic tank leaks, agricultural runoff, and untreated wastewater discharges (Islam et al., 2021). Qadri and Faiq (2020) reported that water contamination has substantially decreased water quality. Due to the negative impacts on the economy, public health, agricultural security, drinking water supply, and biodiversity, water contamination has recently emerged as one of the most serious ecological concerns worldwide (dela Peña et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020).

Figure 1: The Importance of water bodies.

The WHO projected that food and water infected by bacteria like *E. coli* were the primary cause of diarrheal diseases, which killed 485,000 people a year (WHO, 2023). The WHO reported that approximately 37% of Indians living in cities and 64% of Indians living in rural areas lack access to safe drinking water (Akoto and Adiyiah, 2007). Parvin et al. (2022) reported that high rains, flooding, and the proximity of latrines to the tube well are all responsible for the presence of microbes in the drinking water supply. In a previous investigation, the presence of Salmonella and *E. coli* was found in the Punorvoba River (33.33% and 55.55%), Atari River (31.03% and 50.00%), Dhepa River (30.19% and 56.60%), Ghorveshori River (29.63% and 59.26%), and Kakra River (27.08% and 56.25%) (Faridullah et al., 2022). According to recent studies, all residential areas in Dhaka may be vulnerable to faecal pollution, regardless of their location or socioeconomic status (Amin et al., 2019). A comparative investigation on the prevalence and amounts of several pathogenic and indicator bacteria in the surface water of a Canadian river was published by Wilkes et al. (2009). Significant correlations were discovered between all indicator bacteria, including *E. coli*, *Enterococcus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, and total and faecal coliforms, using data compiled over the course of the multi-year investigation. A study of the microbiology of

a contaminated river (Febros) in the northwest Portuguese region of Great Oporto was described by Cabral and Marques (2006). There was a strong correlation between enterococci, faecal streptococci, and total faecal coliforms. A list of common water-borne diseases is presented in Figure 2 and Table 1.

2.2. Common waterborne pathogens

Worldwide, microorganism-mediated water pollution has been identified as one of the biggest threats to the aquatic ecosystem (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020; Ramírez-Castillo et al., 2015). The common waterborne pathogens includes:

2.2.1. Waterborne viral pathogens

Waterborne viruses are more likely than bacteria to stay in the environment, which is why they frequently cause diarrheal illness (Gibson, 2014). Hepatitis A and E viruses, rotavirus (RV), norovirus, adenovirus (AdV), astrovirus (AstV), and other enteroviruses and caliciviruses, such as polioviruses and coxsackieviruses, are all considered water-transmitted viral pathogens with moderate to high health significance by the WHO (Nwachuku and Gerba, 2004; WHO, 2011). The genera *Alphatorquevirus*, *Cyclo-*

Table 1: Waterborne diseases: causes, signs, and manifestations (Adopted from Some et al., 2021)

Causative Agents	Name of Diseases	Symptoms	References
Bacteria			
Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i> (EHEC) serotype O157:H7	Bloody Diarrhoea	Gastrointestinal disorders and hemolytic uremic syndrome	Nguyen and Sperandio, 2012
Enteropathogenic <i>E. coli</i> (EPEC)	Diarrhoea	Gastrointestinal disorders	Ochoa and Contreras, 2011
<i>V. cholerae</i> of serogroup O1 and O139	Cholera	Watery diarrhoea and vomiting	Silva and Benitez, 2016
Enterotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i> (ETEC)	Diarrhoea	Gastrointestinal disorders	Qadri et al., 2005
Enteroinvasive <i>E. coli</i> (EIEC)	Diarrhoea	Gastrointestinal disorders	Rolland et al., 1998
<i>Shigella</i> spp. (<i>S. dysenteriae.</i> , <i>S. boydii</i> , <i>S. flexneri</i> , and <i>S. sonnie</i>)	Shigellosis	Bacillary Dysentery	Khan et al., 2014
Enteraggregative <i>E. coli</i> (EAEC)	Watery Diarrhoea	Gastrointestinal disorders	Kaur et al., 2010
<i>Salmonella paratyphi</i> and <i>Salmonella typhi</i>	Typhoid and Paratyphoid	Enteric Fever	Nasstrom et al., 2014
Protozoa			
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Cryptosporidiasis		Wini, 2019
<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	Amoebic dysentery		
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	Giardiasis		
Viruses			
Hepatitis A virus	Hepatitis		Wini, 2019
<i>Poliovirus</i>	Poliomyelitis		
Helminths			
<i>Dracunculus medinensis</i>	Dracunculiasis		Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020
<i>Fasciola hepatica</i> , <i>Fasciola gigantica</i>	Fascioliasis		

Figure 2: Most common water-borne diseases.

virus, Erythroparvovirus, Bocaparvovirus, Protoparvovirus, Alphapapillomavirus, Betapapillomavirus, Picobirnavirus, Betapolyomavirus, and Alphapolyomavirus are among the ten new viruses that the GWPP (Global Water Pathogen Project) identified in 2017 as having the ability to spread through water (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020).

Noroviruses (NoVs): Noroviruses (NoVs), formerly known as Norwalk virus, were initially discovered among adults and children in the town of Norwalk (Adler and Zickl, 1969). They are a group of single-stranded, non-enveloped, icosahedral RNA viruses that range in size from 27 to 32 nm and belong to the genus *Norovirus* of the family *Caliciviridae*. Projectile vomiting, diarrhea, and occasionally a low-grade fever, headache, and malaise are all brought on by NoVs. Typically, symptoms endure between 24 and 72 hours and are self-limiting. Although the incubation period is typically 24 to 48 hours, reports have shown that symptoms might appear as quickly as 10 hours after exposure. Eating infected seafood or drinking water containing these viruses has been linked to disease outbreaks (Boxman et al., 2006; Maunula et al., 2005).

Rotaviruses (RVs): Rotaviruses (RVs) are double-stranded, non-enveloped viruses that are members of the

Reoviridae family. The outer capsid, inner capsid, and core make up the RV, while the genome is made up of 11 double-stranded RNA segments that code for five non-structural and six structural proteins (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020). An estimated 2 million children are hospitalized and 450,000 die from RV each year, with developing nations in Asia and Africa accounting for the majority of these deaths (Liu et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2014). To lessen the burden of disease, the WHO has advised that RV vaccines be used in routine vaccination programs across the globe (WHO, 2009).

Sapoviruses: Named after the Japanese city of Sapporo, where it was initially identified, *Sapovirus* (SaV) is one of the causative agents of human gastroenteritis (Chiba et al., 1979). SaV is an RNA virus that belongs to the *Caliciviridae* family and has a non-segmented, positive-sense, single-stranded RNA molecule that is roughly 7.3–7.5 kb in size. Disease outbreaks have been documented in people of all ages, including the elderly (Lee et al., 2012). SaVs can spread from person to person through contaminated food and drink, as well as via faecal-oral routes (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020).

Hepatovirus A (HAV): *Hepatovirus A* (HAV), a member of the *Picornaviridae* family, is a nonenveloped virus with an icosahedral capsid measuring roughly 27–32 nm. It is single-stranded and has an RNA genome of roughly 7.5 kb. Type A viral hepatitis is caused by HAV, and there is only one serotype known to exist (Cristina and Costa-Mattioli, 2007). Through the faecal-oral route, the virus is spread by direct contact with an infected individual, contaminated water exposure, or contaminated food consumption (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020).

2.2.2. Waterborne bacterial pathogens

Worldwide, bacterial infections are commonly considered causative agents of waterborne illnesses. These organisms can be found in both humid soils and aquatic environments.

Vibrio: *Vibrios* are facultative anaerobes that are tiny, curved, or rod-shaped, and have one polar flagellum, a Gram-negative, nonspore-forming member of the *Vibrionaceae* family of the *Vibrionales* order, measuring roughly $1.5 - 3.0\mu m \times 0.5\mu m$. The pili (fimbriae) structures found in *Vibrio cholerae*, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, and *Vibrio vulnificus* cells are made of the protein TcpA. There are

about 12 *Vibrio* species that can infect people. There are three bacteria that can cause diarrhea or gastrointestinal tract infections: *Vibrio fluvialis*, *Grimontia hollisae* (formerly *Vibrio hollisae*), and *Vibrio mimicus*. Among microbiological waterborne infections, cholera is the most common and has been known since the 19th century and a widely varied bacterial species is *V. cholerae* (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020; Nwabor et al., 2016).

Salmonella: *Salmonellae*, which belong to the family Enterobacteriaceae of the order Enterobacteriales, are rod-shaped, motile by peritrichous flagella, and are Gram-negative, non-spore-forming bacteria that range in size from 0.7 – 1.5 μm . Antigens O, H, and Vi are among the endotoxins found in *Salmonellae* (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020).

Shigella: *Shigella* are rod-shaped, nonmotile, Gram-negative, nonspore-forming, and members of the family Enterobacteriaceae of the order Enterobacteriales. Their cells are 0.4–0.6 μm by 1.0–3.0 μm in length. *Shigella* can be divided into four serogroups: *Shigella dysenteriae* (serogroup A) has 1–15 serotypes, *Shigella flexneri* (serogroup B) has 4–9 subtypes, *Shigella boydii* (serogroup C) has 1–19 serotypes, and *Shigella sonnei* (serogroup D) has 1 serotype.

Shigella is the natural cause of shigellosis, also known as bacillary dysentery. This disease primarily affects underdeveloped displaced people who lack access to basic sanitary facilities. It can be transmitted by direct contact with an infected person or by faecal contamination of food or drinking water (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020). *Shigella* is thought to be responsible for between 80 and 165 million infections and 60,000 fatalities annually worldwide (Garcia-Williams et al., 2024). Considering the wide variety of *Shigella* species and serogroups found throughout the nation (India), multivalent or cross-protective *Shigella* vaccinations are necessary to reduce the incidence of shigellosis in India (Taneja and Mewara, 2016).

Escherichia: Gram-negative, rod-shaped bacteria that do not generate spores are members of the family Enterobacteriaceae and order Enterobacteriales. *E. coli* is frequently reported to be between 2.0 and 0.5 μm in diameter. *E. coli* is a normal and necessary component of the bacterial flora

in human and animal guts. Certain serotypes of *E. coli* play a part in intestinal and extra-intestinal illnesses, such as urinary tract infections; however, the majority of strains that live in the colon are not harmful. *E. coli* can be detected using Polymerase Chain Reaction, Microarray assay, Biosensors, etc. (Lee et al., 2008; Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020; Min and Baeumner, 2002; Ramírez-Castillo et al., 2015; Tsen et al., 1998).

Burkholderia: The bacteria in the genus *Burkholderia* belong to the family Burkholderiaceae of the order Burkholderiales. They are rod-shaped, straight or slightly curved, non-spore-forming, Gram-negative, and motile because of one or more polar flagella, except one species. There are 60 species of obligate aerobes in the genus, which are water pathogens that are common in nature. *Burkholderia gladioli*, *Burkholderia mallei*, *Burkholderia pseudomallei*, and *Burkholderia cepacia* complex species are among the species that are clinically significant. *B. pseudomallei*, which has a diameter of 0.8 μm and a length of 1.5 μm , can be found in both surface and ground water. The fatal condition known as melioidosis is brought on by *B. pseudomallei* (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020).

Campylobacter: *Campylobacter* is one of the common waterborne pathogens. These are Gram-negative, 0.5–8 μm long, and 0.2–0.5 μm wide. The bacteria in the genus *Campylobacter* belong to the family Campylobacteraceae in the order Campylobacterales and are distinguished by their curved, spiral, or S-shaped cells. There are 12 subspecies and 29 species in this genus. *Campylobacter jejuni* is the most significant species of *Campylobacter* in human gastroenteritis, followed by *Campylobacter coli*, *Campylobacter lari*, and *Campylobacter fetus*. A total of 8.5% of the overall burden of diarrheal illness was caused by *Campylobacter enteritis*, which ranked fourth in terms of causes after RV, *cryptosporidiosis*, and *E. coli* diarrhea (combined enterotoxigenic and enteropathogenic *E. coli* infections) (Murray et al., 2012; Semenza and Ko, 2023).

Leptospira: There are now 20 species in the genus *Leptospira*, which is a member of the family Leptospiraceae of the phylum Spirochaete. Nine of these species are pathogenic, six are saprophytic, and five are intermediate. They are motile, thin, tightly wound spirochetes that are typically 6–20 μm long, though they can create consid-

erably longer cells when cultured (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020). Since multiple illness outbreaks have been documented during the rainy season, leptospirosis is fundamentally a waterborne infection. Because they may endure for extended periods of time in freshwater and moist soil, both pathogenic and saprophytic strains of leptospirosis have been identified from water sources, such as rivers and lakes. *Leptospira* can live in soil or water for months and are transmitted via the urine of infected animals (Pal and Hadush, 2017; Semenza and Ko, 2023).

2.2.3. Potential waterborne helminths

Helminths are invertebrates that belong to the Kingdom Animalia and are commonly referred to as parasitic worms. They have round, flat, or elongated bodies. The phylums Nematoda (roundworms) and Platyhelminthes (trematodes) include the majority of parasitic helminths. Worldwide, helminth parasites infect a significant number of humans and animals, primarily in underdeveloped nations where access to clean water, sanitary facilities, and hygienic practices is lacking. *Fasciola* spp. (*Fasciola hepatica* and *Fasciola gigantica*) are liver flukes and *Dracunculus medinensis* (Guinea worm) are the two main helminths that can be spread through drinking water (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020).

2.2.4. Waterborne protozoan pathogens

The most common etiologic agents found in waterborne disease organisms during the 1990s were protozoan parasites. *Giardia lamblia* was also the most often found pathogen from 1978 to 1991, however in 1992, the number of outbreaks reported for cryptosporidiosis and giardiasis was equal. Additionally regarded as causative agents in waterborne disease outbreaks (WBDOs) are *Naegleria fowleri*, *Acanthamoeba* spp., and *Entamoeba histolytica* (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020; WHO, 2008).

Microsporidia: *Microsporidia* are members of the phylum Microspora, which parasitize all major animal groups, comprise more than 140 genera and 1200 species. They are spore-forming, obligatory intracellular protists. Two of the most common species linked to human gastrointestinal disorders are *Enterocytozoon bieneusi* and *Encephalitozoon*, out of the 14 human pathogenic *Microsporidia* species (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020; Nwachuku and Gerba, 2004).

Figure 3: The image showing common water borne pathogens.

***Cystoisospora belli*:** Coccidian parasites called *Cystoisospora* (previously *Isospora*) are primarily found in tropical and subtropical regions and are members of the phylum Apicomplexa (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020). Although several species of *Cystoisospora* can infect animals, only humans are known to be the host of *C. belli* (Lindsay et al., 1997).

***Giardia*:** The phylum Metamonada contains the flagellated protozoan parasites known as *Giardia*, which cause giardiasis, a diarrheal illness that affects humans and other mammals worldwide. Six *Giardia* species have been identified since 1920; the most common pathogen in humans is *Giardia duodenalis*, also known as *Giardia intestinalis* and *G. lamblia*. They can spread by direct faecal-oral contact, contaminated food, or water (Magana-Arachchi and Wanigatunge, 2020; Onyango et al., 2018). Figure 3 and Figure 4 illustrate the common water-borne pathogens, their modes of transmission, and infection sites.

2.3. Organisms indicating water pollution

Drinking contaminated water may cause new cases of the disease if there are infectious disease carriers among the

Figure 4: A brief overview of the major waterborne pathogens, their transmission routes, and areas of infection.

faecal contaminants. As a sign of faecal pollution, the common intestinal excremental organisms are nearly always more numerous than these harmful ones. If indicator organisms are not found in the water, then disease-causing microbes are probably not present as well (Dongzagla et al., 2021; Wanjugi et al., 2016). One of the main problems with the hygienic quality of drinking and recreational water is microbial pollution in the water body. One of the biggest risks to human health is the existence of viruses, bacteria, and protozoa. Careful consideration of the relationship between energy, drinking water, and health is necessary to ensure a nation's socioeconomic success. Water, energy, and food (WEF) are interdependent and require interdisciplinary research because of their direct and indirect effects on one another. In light of the aforementioned pressing situation, it is crucial to preserve and manage freshwater resources (Some et al., 2021). Definitions of key faecal indicator Microorganisms are given in Table 2.

2.3.1. Total coliforms

The total coliform count is one of the best indicators of water pollution. It has long been standard practice to utilize the total coliform count technique as a water safety indicator. The WHO states that the acceptable limits of *E.*

coli and coliform for drinking water are 0/100 ml and 126 CFU/100 ml for home and recreational use, respectively (Gunda and Mitra, 2016). Drinking water should have a total and faecal coliform count of 0/100 ml, following the Bureau of Indian Standards' recommendations. For both basic and applied research in aquatic microbial ecology as well as the creation of parameter-based technologies for the assessment of drinking water quality, the enumeration technique of faecal bacteria is essential (Ramos-Ramirez et al., 2021). Total coliforms are a class of gram-negative, facultative anaerobic, aerobic bacteria that can ferment lactose at 37°C and create gas and acid in less than 24 hours. *Escherichia*, *Klebsiella*, *Enterobacter*, *Serratia*, *Citrobacter*, and *Edwardsiella* are among the group's members. Faecal coliforms, also known as thermotolerant coliforms, are a subgroup of total coliforms that can digest lactose at 44.5°C, setting them apart from total coliforms. The group members are *Klebsiella* and *E. coli*. The thermotolerant coliform *E. coli* can manufacture indole from tryptophan at 44 ±0.5 °C, responds positively to the methyl red test, cannot synthesize acetyl-methyl carbinol, and does not rely solely on citrate as a carbon source. The use of the coliform group as an indicator of faecal contamination is governed by strict rules. The most prevalent coliform in warm-blooded animals intestinal flora is *E. coli*, whose prevalence may be

Table 2: Characteristics of key faecal Indicator Microorganisms (Adopted from Saxena et al. (2015))

Characteristics/Features	Indicator Organisms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An anaerobic, non-spore-forming, Gram-negative, pleiomorphic bacillus, has been proposed as human-specific indicator. 	<i>Bacteroides</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gram-negative, non-spore-forming, oxidase/indole-negative, rod-shaped facultative anaerobic bacteria that ferment lactose (with β-galactosidase) to acid and gas within 24–48 h at $36 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in a medium containing bile salts and detergents. Not specific indicators of faecal pollution. Not specific indicators of faecal pollution. 	Total coliforms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thermotolerant coliforms that produce acid and gas from lactose fermentation at $44.5 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ within 24 ± 2 h. It is also known as faecal coliforms due to their role as faecal indicators. 	Faecal coliforms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gram-positive, catalase-negative non-spore-forming cocci from selective media (e.g., azide dextrose broth (sodium azide =strong inhibitor of respiratory chain) or m-Enterococcus agar) that grow on bile aesculin agar and at 45°C. Belonging to the genera Enterococcus and Streptococcus possessing the Lancefield group D antigen. This group had been used in conjunction with faecal coliform to determine the source of recent faecal contamination (man or animals). 	Faecal streptococci (FS)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The subset of faecal streptococci that grow at pH 9.6, 10 and 45°C and in 6.5% NaCl. The enterococci are generally found in lower numbers than other indicator organisms; however, they exhibit better survival in sea water. 	Enterococci
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gram-positive spore-forming, non-motile, strict anaerobe, sulfite-reducing bacilli, ferment lactose, sucrose and inositol with the production of gas, produce stormy clot fermentation with milk, reduce nitrate, hydrolyze gelatin and produce lecithinase and acid phosphatase. Spores most often of faecal origin and always present in sewage. These indicate the presence of Protozoa and Enteroviruses. 	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>

Characteristics/Features

Indicator Organisms

- Not all sulphite-reducing clostridia (SRC) in receiving waters are indicators of faecal pollution, hence *C. perfringens* is the appropriate indicator.
- Bacterial viruses which are ubiquitous in the environment and resistant to disinfection.
- For water quality testing and to model human enteric viruses and protozoans, most interest in somatic coliphages, male-specific RNA coliphages (F-RNA coliphages) and phages infecting *B. fragilis*.
- Gram-positive, obligate anaerobic, non-acid-fast, non-spore-forming, non-motile bacilli which are highly pleomorphic and may exhibit branching bulbs (bifids), clubs, coccoid, coryneform, Y and V forms.
- They are all catalase-negative and ferment lactose (except the three insect species; *B. asteroides*, *B. indicum* and *B. coryneforme*) and one of the most numerous groups of bacteria in the feces of warm-blooded animals.

Bacteriophages (phages)

Bifidobacteria

primarily linked to faecal contamination. Thus, drinking water cannot include any *E. coli* (Rompre et al., 2002). Certain serotypes of *E. coli* such as O157:H7, are harmful to both people and animals and can result in severe diarrhea and sepsis. Another Gram-negative, non-spore-forming, aerobic, facultatively anaerobic microorganism *Salmonella*, is a member of the Enterobacteriaceae family (Lin et al., 2022). Definitions for indicator and index microorganisms of public health concern and indicator organisms used to establish the performance criteria for various water uses are given in Figure 5. Several researchers have offered conventional microbiological indicators, but they have a number of drawbacks and are not suitable for use in all types of water. In this case, more individuals 'Alternative' catalysts should be employed to identify potential health risks (Figueras and Borrego, 2010; WHO, 2004; WHO, 2008).

2.3.2. Sulphite-reducing clostridia

According to WHO (2008) and Figueras et al. (2008), the genus *Clostridium* (*C. perfringens*) can be used as a marker of faecal contamination and hygienic quality of water based on the assumptions that follow: (a) they are more stable in environmental water and more resistant to disinfection techniques than most pathogens; (b) they are successfully

used to monitor sewage contamination in water as these indicator microorganisms are present in the excreta of all warm-blooded animals and are also found in sewage.

2.3.3. Bifidobacterium

One of the most prevalent and most varied types of bacteria found in warm-blooded animals feces is *Bifidobacterium* spp. (Bonjoch et al., 2004; Wilson, 2005). Numerous colonies of Bifidobacteria are found in human and some animal feces. A number of *Bifidobacterium* species are unique to humans or animals. *Bifidobacterium suis* has only been detected in the feces of piglets, *Bifidobacterium gallinarum* and *Bifidobacterium pullorum* in the intestines of hens, and *Bifidobacterium cuniculi* and *magnum* in rabbit faecal samples. The species composition of human feces varies with an individual's age. Infants' intestines are typically dominated by *B. breve* and *B. longum*. The four major species in adults are *B. adolescentis*, *B. catenulatum*, *B. pseudocatenulatum*, and *B. longum*. Bifidobacteria are consistently far more prevalent than coliforms in both human and animal feces (Biavati and Mattarelli, 2003; Cabral, 2010; Sinton et al., 1998; Wilson, 2005). Because some species of Bifidobacteria are unique to humans and animals (Cabral, 2010; King et al., 2007; Wery et al., 2010), the presence of these species in the water environ-

Figure 5: Organisms that serve as indicators and are utilized to set performance standards for various applications of water.

ment is thought to be an indicator of faecal contamination of water. In addition, some species are a substitute water quality indicators in tropical and temperate regions (Mushi et al., 2010; Stewart et al., 2008).

2.3.4. *Bacteroides*

Among the total anaerobic microflora present in the human Gastrointestinal tract, *Bacteroides* are among the microorganisms that are most oxygen-tolerant. Until now, the use of anaerobic *Bacteroides* species as a faecal indicator has been restricted by the requirement to maintain anoxic conditions for cultivation, isolation, and biochemical identification. In aquatic conditions, *Bacteroides* often have a substantially lower survival rate than coliforms (Cabral, 2010; Wilson, 2005).

A new polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based indicator system has been developed to identify the source of faecal pollution in fresh and marine waters. It uses molecular markers from the *Bacteroides* group of faecal anaerobic bacteria (Bower et al., 2005; Field et al., 2003; Fogarty and Voytek, 2005; Sauer et al., 2011). This technique allows for the differentiation of many possible sources of pollution by detecting genetic marker sequences that are distinct to both the host species and the faecal bacteria. Addition-

ally, this approach is quick and precise and does not require the isolation and growth of the indicator bacteria. According to findings on the identification of human- and bovine-specific *Bacteroides-Prevotella* 16S rRNA genetic markers using length heterogeneity-PCR and terminal-restriction fragment length polymorphism, these genetic markers may be used to identify the source of faecal pollution human or bovine (Bernhard and Field, 2000; Zheng et al., 2013). Human-specific *Bacteroides* genetic markers in environmental samples have been quantified using realtime PCR techniques (Okabe et al., 2007; Seurinck et al., 2006).

2.3.5. Bacteriophages

Bacteriophages have been proposed as models to assess the chlorination efficiency of water treatment plants and as an indicator of viral and faecal contamination (Duran et al., 2003; Leclerc et al., 2000). Somatic coliphages, F (male)-specific RNA bacteriophages (F-RNA phages), and *Bacteroides fragilis* phages are among the suggested categories (Duran et al., 2003). Since they are particular to *E. coli*, somatic coliphages are frequently utilized to detect sewage and/or feces contamination in a variety of water sources. In order to locate the source of contamination in surface water and aquifers, these are also utilized as biotracers (Muniesa et al., 2012).

2.3.6. Heterotrophic plate count

Among the earliest metrics to be used to evaluate the "purity" of source water in the late 1800s, were the total aerobic bacteria or heterotrophic plate count (HPC) (Bartram et al., 2003; Maal-Bared et al., 2008). But these are no longer utilized as indicators of health (Edberg et al., 1989; Verhille, 2013). They are now used by the Drinking Water Distribution System (DWDS) (WHO, 2004; WHO, 2008) as a general indicator of water quality. Currently, notable alterations in HPC function as a warning indicator for potential declines in water quality, prompting additional research (Bartram et al., 2003; Verhille, 2013).

2.3.7. Emerging waterborne bacterial pathogens

Newly emerging waterborne pathogens present a serious risk to public health in both industrialized and developing nations. Waterborne diseases are becoming more and more prevalent, which poses a major concern to drinking water safety. Therefore, it is imperative to devise methods for identifying these possibly developing aquatic diseases. The persistent rise in waterborne pathogens could be attributed to various factors, including: (a) development of molecular techniques for source tracking and detection; (b) a rise in susceptible populations; (c) globalization of trade and travel; (d) molecular evolution (genetic re-assortment); (e) modifications in drinking water treatment technology; (f) shifts in food production and supply; and (g) multi-drug resistance (Chugh, 2008; Morens and Fauci, 2013; Sharma et al., 2003; Sherchand, 2012; Skovgaard, 2007).

Water borne pathogens like environmental mycobacteria, aeromonads (*Aeromonas sobria*, *A. caviae* and *A. hydrophila*), *Legionella pneumophila*, *Vibrio* spp. (*V. cholerae* O139 and *V. cholerae* O1), pathogenic *E. coli* (enteroinvasive *E. coli*, enteropathogenic *E. coli*, enteroaggregative *E. coli* and shiga toxin producing *E. coli*), *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Helicobacter pylori*, multidrug resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Campylobacter jejuni* have the potential to be spread through the supply of drinking water (Saxena et al., 2015).

As an alternative indicator of faecal contamination, some faecal organic compounds, including sterols, have been proposed (Furtula et al., 2012; Isobe et al., 2002; Isobe et al., 2004; Zheng et al., 2013). One of the main faecal sterols expelled in feces is coprostanol (5β -cholestan-

3β -ol), which is produced by natural microflora, or native bacteria, found in the intestines of humans and animals (Cabral, 2010). It reveals the presence of bacteria in water environments. Its measurement has been suggested as a potent technique for tracking fresh faecal contamination in tropical regions of Japan, Malaysia, and Vietnam (Ashbolt, 2001; Derrien et al., 2012; Isobe et al., 2002; Isobe et al., 2004). Coprostanol is easily associated with water and sewage particles due to its hydrophobic nature. As a result, faecal sterols could be integrated into sediments and maintained for a very long period in anoxic environments without experiencing considerable biodegradation (stable for 450 days at 15°C) (Isobe et al., 2002). The discovery that coprostanol was also detected far from the potential source of faecal pollution is explained by all of these details. Therefore, coprostanol, which is mostly found in sediments, may be a sign of distant or ancient faecal pollution (Savichtcheva and Okabe, 2006). Furthermore, the current large-scale application of faecal steroids is limited by the lack of studies on the application of host specificity, desirable detection sensitivity, and correlation with pathogens. These findings suggest the need for further research (Saxena et al., 2015). Yi et al. (2023) highlight the importance of artificial intelligence combined with machine learning, rapid response biosensor-based technologies, and very sensitive molecular diagnostics in providing crucial data for efficient water quality monitoring, assessment, and intervention. Hence there are several techniques used for the identification of pathogens (Table 3).

2.4. Strategies minimizing waterborne illness outbreaks in developing countries

The following tactics (Table 4) are employed as low-cost substitutes in poor nations and are successful in stopping the spread of water borne diseases (WHO, 2007). Microbial pollution in the water body is one of the major issues concerning the sanitary quality of drinking and recreational water. The presence of pathogenic bacteria, protozoa, and viruses is one of the serious threats to human health. To secure the socio-economic progress of a country, the connection between energy, drinking water, and health must be considered carefully. The fact that water, energy, and food (WEF) all influence each other, both directly and indirectly, requires interdisciplinary study into the WEF nexus. Thus, it is important to conserve and manage the fresh water resources in this afore-mentioned burning issue (Some et al., 2021).

Table 3: Techniques for the detection of pathogens and indicators from water, wastewater and other environmental samples

Molecular Techniques	Conventional Techniques
Ribotyping	Microscopy
Highly reproducible; classify isolates from multiple sources	Simple, rapid and direct observation of microbial cells
Complex, expensive; labor intensive; geographically specific	
Amplified ribosomal DNA restriction analysis (ARDRA)	Culture-dependent methods
Culture-independent technique and suitable for analysis of a variety of microbes	Easy to identify the individual microbes
Ribosomal RNA intergenic spacer analysis (RISA)	Microbial indicator-based pathogen estimation
Culture-independent technique, suitable for analysis of a variety of microbes and gives remarkable heterogeneity in length and sequence among bacteria	Easy to perform, current standard for coliform has been established
Pulse-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE)	
Extremely reproducible and highly sensitive to point genetic difference	
Denaturing-gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE)	
Culture-independent technique, suitable for analysis of a variety of microbes and use rRNA gene sequence heterogeneity	
Terminal-restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis (T-RFLP)	
Fast, semi-quantitative, culture-independent technique and suitable for analysis of a variety of microbes	
Fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH)	
Quantitative and directly visualize the microbial cells including non-culturables	

Molecular Techniques

Conventional Techniques

Quantitative PCR (qPCR)

Culture-independent technique and suitable for analysis of a variety of microbes

Repetitive DNA sequences (Rep-PCR)

Simple and rapid

Length heterogeneity-PCR (LH-PCR)

Culture-independent technique

Multiplex PCR (mPCR)

Fast and simultaneous detection of several target microorganisms

Nucleic acid microarrays

High throughput design with wider applications

Host-specific 16S rDNA

Does not require culturing or a database; indicator of recent pollution

On-chip technology

Combination of PCR with nucleic acid hybridization on a single chip and less interference between parallel reactions

2.5. Conclusion and recommendations

Water is a vital resource for human survival and a productive tool for economic growth. Unimproved water sources that are contaminated pose a global threat to the quality of drinking water. With poor hygiene habits leading to illnesses in humans. Providing safe drinking water to everyone is one of the biggest problems of the twenty-first century. The human health implications of assessing drinking water quality based on aesthetic features and water quality metrics are significant. A household's perception

of the water quality was used to assess aesthetic parameters such as color, odor, and taste. Almost all water sources have been contaminated with total and faecal coliforms, with the exception of well-treated tap water.

Microorganisms like bacteria, viruses, or parasites can all cause waterborne diseases. In developing nations, diarrhea, giardiasis, dysentery, and gastroenteritis are prevalent diseases brought on by these pathogenic microorganisms. Water that is appropriate for human consumption is devoid of harmful chemicals and microorganisms that might cause

Table 4: Strategies minimizing waterborne illness outbreaks in developing countries

Methods	Description
Chlorination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chlorine, a disinfectant, is added in liquid or tablet form to destroy pathogenic germs found in drinking water (DW) supply reservoirs. This is a commonly used way of purifying water.
Boiling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is the most traditional and widely used method of disinfecting water in homes that kills the majority of the bacteria responsible for diseases associated with the intestine related diseases.
Solar disinfection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This kind of portable water treatment system is sometimes referred to as point-of-use water treatment. Using this procedure, the clear DW in throwaway clear plastic bottles is left outside in the sun for a full day. Generally, the pathogens found in water are rendered inactive by the combination of heat and UV light from the sun.
Filtration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water is purified using premium ceramic filters with small pores that are frequently coated with silver. Studies have shown that these filters are quite successful at getting rid of bacteria and other suspended solid particles. By limiting patient exposure or acting as a barrier against potentially dangerous waterborne pathogens, these devices can be placed immediately at water outlets to safeguard users. Filters must be routinely cleaned in order to preserve the water flow.
Combined flocculation/ disinfection systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The process involves adding chlorine to water in the form of tablets or powder, followed by a timed release of chlorine to coagulate and flocculate any sediments. It is especially useful for treating murky water. In order to fully disinfect the water, it is often agitated for a few minutes, strained to separate the flocculants, and left to stand for an additional thirty minutes.
Safe storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research suggests that even healthy water at the time of collection is frequently contaminated with feces during collection, transportation, and domestic use mostly by unclean hands. Thus, safe storage is must needed to avoid contamination.

illness. Although water is a common and abundant natural resource, access to safe drinking water is not always guaranteed. For all plants, animals, and humans, water is necessary. High-quality water is essential for human productivity and longevity. Therefore, maintaining water quality is crucial. Control, monitoring, and implementation of water quality regulations are urgently needed because pathogens in water continue to be the main cause of serious illness and death. More effective pathogen detection and health risk assessment must be included in order to reach the objective of pathogen-free water to protect public health.

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Author Contributions

A. A, Mohamed Hatha and K. Soumya conceptualized the review. Material preparation and data collection were performed by Medwin Mathew, K.G, Sabareesh Kumar, and K. Soumya. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

This is a review article and data that support the findings of this study are from published research papers. Datasets cited in the references that are publicly available. Data-sets or materials related to this review article can be accessed from the sources mentioned in the reference list.

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Ethical approval

No need for ethics approval, since this manuscript does not include research on identifiable human material or data.

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